

POLYPHEM

THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

SMALL-SCALE SOLAR

THERMAL COMBINED CYCLE

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It is a great honour and a big pleasure to coordinate this exciting European R&D action. The project POLYPHEM is carried out by a group of highly qualified and enthusiast persons from European research centres and the industry sector. In total, nine partners from four European countries are in charge of the execution of the workplan. A large range of scientific and technical topics are covered in this project: thermal, mechanical and material engineering, process control, numerical simulation, measurement techniques. With the project POLYPHEM, this dynamic international group paves the way to the solar tower plants of future generation.

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Foreword by
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POLYPHEM

LEGAL DISCLAIMER

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■ An introduction to **Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)**

CSP technologies use mirrors or lenses to concentrate sunlight onto a small area receiver where sunlight is converted into thermal energy.

According to how sunlight is concentrated, CSP technologies are classified into line-focusing and point-focusing technologies. The main line-

focusing CSP technologies are **parabolic trough** and **linear Fresnel**, whereas the main point-focusing technologies are **parabolic dish** and **central receiver**.

■ **CSP application**

The main applications of the CSP technologies are power generation, process **heat, cooling, desalination and solar chemistry**. Commercially,

the most widely used application is power generation, known as **Solar Thermal Electricity (STE)**.

■ The challenge for **small-scale CSP Plants**

The **decentralized generation of power on-demand in remote areas at competitive cost** is a major challenge of CSP to which POLYPHEM is all about. This project of **small-scale solar tower** proposes robust technologies of engines forming the combined cycle (micro gas-turbine and ORC), easy-handling heat transfer fluid (thermal oil)

and cheap material for heat storage (concrete). One expectation of this challenging project is to demonstrate the **reliability of the technology** and the **flexibility of the power generation** from solar energy.

- List of acronyms:
CSP Concentrated Solar Power
LCA Life-Cycle Assessment
LCOE Levelized Cost of Energy
ORC Organic Rankine Cycle
μGT Micro Gas-Turbine
TES Thermal Energy Storage
TRL Technology Readiness Level

The four main **CSP technologies**

Parabolic Dish

Parabolic Trough

Linear Fresnel

Solar Tower

POLYPHEM in a nutshell

The main objective of POLYPHEM is to improve:

- ✓ the performance of small-scale Concentrated Solar Power plants
- ✓ their flexibility to generate power on demand.

To this end, a new technology is proposed: a solar-driven combined cycle with integrated thermal energy storage.

The power block considered in POLYPHEM is a combined cycle intended to be used for decentralised small-scale power generation in the range 40 kW to 2000 kW in remote

areas. The purpose is to meet the variable demand of energy of a mini-grid. The baseline technology consists of an air Brayton cycle as top cycle and an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) as bottom cycle.

POLYPHEM broadens this technology by driving the top cycle with solar energy through the development of an advanced technology of pressurized air solar receiver and by including an innovative thermal energy storage unit between both cycles.

Besides electricity generation, other applications will be considered for future developments, such as heating/cooling of multi-family buildings or water desalination for small communities.

THE FINAL RESULT

THIS INNOVATIVE POWER CYCLE WILL BE VALIDATED IN A RELEVANT ENVIRONMENT (TRL 5) AT THE THEMIS SOLAR TOWER IN TARGASSONE, FRANCE. IT WILL ALSO ESTABLISH THE GUIDELINES FOR THE COMMERCIAL DEPLOYMENT OF THIS TECHNOLOGY IN THE LONG TERM.

Prototype plant

60 kW

Thermal storage unit

1,3 MWh

The project concept and innovations

THREE HIGHLY INNOVATIVE IDEAS BEAR THE POLYPHEM CONCEPT

01

Coupling a small-scale Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) with an open Brayton cycle (μGT) to make a novel combined cycle

02

Integrating a low-cost thermal energy storage (TES) between both cycles

03

Integrating a high temperature solar receiver in the top cycle

The top cycle of POLYPHEM is the air Brayton cycle of the micro gas-turbine. This engine is operated on-sun and generates power. The heat recovered at the exhaust of the gas-turbine is directed to the Thermal Energy Storage. The heat is discharged from the storage and is converted into power on-demand by the Organic Rankine Cycle. In option for future commercial versions of POLYPHEM plant, the bottom cycle may be replaced by a heating/cooling or water desalination unit to satisfy alternate energy needs.

A collaborative EU-funded project

POLYPHEM is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The project is funded by the "Secure, clean and efficient energy" programme, under the specific topic "Developing the next generation technologies of renewable electricity and heating/cooling" (LCE-07-2016-2017). The consortium is coordinated by CNRS-PROMES and implemented by a total of 9 partners from 4 EU member countries.

Duration

4

years
from April 2018 to March 2022

EU contribution

4,975

millions €

Consortium

9 partners
4 research centres
5 private companies
4 countries

POLYPHEM Technical Work Plan

POLYPHEM Timeline: key achievements

Expected impacts

TECHNOLOGY IMPACT

- A new design and the next generation of small-scale CSP plants with high performance combined cycle and flexible generation of renewable electricity with firm capacity
- Reduced water requirement compared to steam Rankine cycle
- A higher optical efficiency than any other solar field
- An extended range of designs by varying the size of the components, each design being optimized for a specific need (power generation, cogeneration, heating/cooling, water desalination)

EUROPEAN COMPETITIVENESS

- Strengthening competitiveness and growth of European companies already engaged in CSP related activities
- Supporting the business activity of SMEs by opening a new field in which the early movers will have a decisive competitive advantage over potential competitors
- New business opportunities for industries developing products such as: technical concrete, organic Rankine cycles, high temperature and high-performance heat exchangers, insulating materials, thermal processes

ECONOMIC IMPACT

- The Levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) estimated for the POLYPHEM technology developed at the end of the project (2020-2025) is 21 c€/kWh in sunny regions (2600 kWh/m²/y)
- When commercial technology will be ready in 2030-2040, the LCOE is expected to drop down to 16.5 c€/kWh which will be competitive with the cost of electricity generation in remote areas in Africa, Middle East or India

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

- A solar technology for clean power and process heat generation which will:
 - increase electricity generation based on Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)
 - develop Thermal Energy Storage (TES) systems and integrated energy solutions
 - supply Green technologies
 - use desalination in order to increase water availability
 - contribute to sustainable agricultural and food production
 - reduce CO₂ emissions

SOCIAL IMPACT

- Supply of electricity on-demand through mini-grids and to water supply in isolated and arid regions
- Creation of about 1000 jobs in SMEs in the EU and regions of implementation in the following sectors:
 - Engineering, development and financing
 - Manufacturing and delivery of components
 - Construction of plants, installation and commissioning
 - Operation and maintenance

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